

**RATIO OF INCIDENCE AND ITS RISK FACTORS OF ANAEMIA AMONG
DIFFERENT ETHNIC PREGNANT WOMEN OF QUETTA DISTRICT,
BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN.**

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence and risk factors of anaemia among pregnant women of diverse ethnic backgrounds in Quetta District, Balochistan, Pakistan, were investigated during the period of June 2023 to January 2024. Pregnant women from diverse ethnic backgrounds comprised 526 individuals; among them were 140 Baloch (26.61%), 190 Pashtun (36.12%), 85 Hazara (16.15%), 61 Brahui (11.59%), and 50 Sindhi (9.50%). Blood samples were obtained in Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) tubes from the pathology and haematology departments of Sheikh Khalifah Bin Zayyad Hospital Quetta, Sandeman Provisional Hospital (SPH), and Bolan Medical Complex Hospital (BMCH). Iron deficiency affected 36.12% of the 526 women surveyed, followed by poor nutrition (22.81%), insufficient prenatal care (17.1%), parasite diseases (15.20%), and genetic predisposition (8.74%). The lowest mean haemoglobin level, 9.6 g/dL with a standard deviation of 1.3, is found in those under the age of 20. Compared to the youngest group, those over 35 and those aged 20 to 25 also exhibit comparatively higher mean values. The group of people who are 26–30 years old have the highest mean CRP level (4.1 mg/L) with a standard deviation of 1.4. Finally, the application of targeted programmes, which deal with the socio-economic roots, increase nutrition support, and expand the uptake of prenatal care, is essential in lowering the level of anaemia and improve maternal health indicators in the area.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Anaemia is a condition whereby the body is not able to transport oxygen because of the low concentration of red blood cells or haemoglobin in the blood. This causes symptoms such as fatigue, paleness, and shortness of breath (Murugamoorthy 2019). Women during pregnancy should know that anemia is a risk factor that has negative result on either the mother or the developing foetus. This possible outcome includes premature birth, low birth weight, or maternal death (Ogunbode, O.O., & Ogunbode, N.E., 2021). The low blood volume issue for gestational anemia is more than just a personal inconvenience. It can have deleterious effects on both mothers and their fetuses. Anaemia in mothers can cause weariness, make them more susceptible to infections, and increase the chance of difficulties following childbirth, such as postpartum haemorrhage or even mother death (Shaduka 2022).

Anaemia affects 42% of pregnant women worldwide, which translates to 415 million women who must deal with this issue (Billah2023). With an alarming 56% incidence, Southeast and South Asia exhibit the largest burden (WHO 2023). (Habib et al., 2023) reports that a 2023 study found a 53.7% prevalence among pregnant women in large cities, although World Bank statistics indicates a 49% prevalence in 2019.

According to Signore et al. (2021), mothers are more likely to experience problems during pregnancy and labour, and their infants are more likely to experience morbidity and death. Children with anaemia may have impaired cognitive development, which could limit their potential in the future and perpetuate a cycle of poverty (Sundararajan & Rabe 2021). Studies show that up to 70% of pregnant women in Baluchistan experience nutritional deficiencies as a result of insufficient dietary intake, which is exacerbated by socioeconomic variables such poverty and food insecurity (Ajmal et al., 2022).

However, globally there is more than 50-70% of pregnant women focused on the deficiency of iron, the most common cause. A folate insufficiency may affect up to 20% of pregnant women at the same time as an iron deficiency. Despite being less widespread, the problem of developing the deficiency of vitamin B12 can hit if the diet consists of low amounts of meat and dairy products (Kiely et al., 2021).

Hess et al. (2023) said that in addition to hookworm, malaria and HIV/AIDS, chronic illnesses and disorders can be the causes of anaemia in 20–50% of the cases, depending on the infection and setting. Therefore, up to 20% of women may happen to be iron deficient after two consecutive pregnancies together based on Mintz et al. (2020). Despite the fact that the blood might have been lost as a former result of delivery or during menstruation,

there is no exact rate of loss depicting the disease in those specific situations. According to the data from the World Health Organization (WHO), 62 billion of the world's population (about one-fourth) suffer from anaemia . It was foreseen, that majority of 468 million reproductive women, who were not carrying any babies, are going to be affected by the disease out of all them. It has been stated that the rate of anaemia varies from one country to the other with a number of reports indicating prevalence rates ranging from 4 in 5 people to those as high as 9 in 10 people. 0 to 7. Even in the USA which is an affluent country, not a single person is fully satisfied (Abdullah et al. , 2020).

Based on the aetiology, anaemia can be classified into four categories by Sarna et al. (2020): to total iron deficiency anemia (IDA), aplastic anaemia, anaemia from chronic disorders, anaemia from blood losses and anemia from enhanced hemolysis (the breakdown of red blood cells). Iron deficiency (ID) has been the cause of 50% anaemia cases known in the global scale. Canceric kidney disease (CKD), diabetes mellitus, cancer, autoimmune diseases, and persistent infections are some of the illnesses that cause anaemia of chronic diseases, or ACD. A case of hypersplenism (and consequent sequestration and destruction of normal red blood cells) is indicative of anemia and can be found in patients with hemolytic anemia and chronic bleeding conditions such as bleeding gastric ulcers. Inadequate or null red cell production as is the case with either bone marrow aplasia or clonal blood diseases underlies apalatctic anaemia.

1. Research Methodology

1.1. Research Design

A recent study was carried out at Sheikh Khalifah Bin Zayyad Hospital Quetta, Sandeman Provisional Hospital (SPH), and Bolan Medical Complex Hospital (BMCH), among other facilities in the Quetta province. In all, 526 female patients of reproductive age received diagnoses between June 2023 and January 2024. The patients were interviewed using a questionnaire that included their full name, age, place of residence, education, husband's job, socioeconomic status, ethnicity, and signs and symptoms (such as exhaustion, headaches, dyspnea, palpitations, pallor, tachycardia, and tongue smoothness were also recorded). Additionally, the patients' gravidity, para, and dietary intake were recorded.

1.2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Healthy pregnant women from the Quetta district, ranging in age from 18 to 40 at various stages of pregnancy, were chosen based on their haemoglobin level, which had to be less than 11 g/dl. Women over 40, those with a history of blood loss or blood transfusion during

the current pregnancy, women with other chronic conditions, obesity, hypertension, gestational diabetes mellitus, and any other severe illness were not allowed to get pregnant.

1.3. Sample Collection

A total of 526 pregnant women in varying stages of pregnancy had blood samples taken. In tubes containing ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), blood samples were obtained. A total of 526 ladies had their haemoglobin levels determined. The pathology and haematology laboratories of Sandeman Provisional Hospital (SPH), Bolan Medical Complex Hospital (BMCH), and Sheikh Khalifah Bin Zayyad Hospital Quetta used a haematology analyzer (BC 3000 Plus Auto haematology analyzer, MINDRAY: Bio-medical Electronics company Ltd., Shenzhen China) to measure haemoglobin levels. Blood samples were taken out, gathered, and labelled in EDTA vials before being processed in the lab. After inserting the samples into the analyzer, automated measurement was started. Results from participants were entered into the laboratory information system. The outcomes were compared to the historical data, and any deviations—such as an unusual decrease in haemoglobin were noted. There were three iterations of the process.

1.4. Measurements of blood iron stores

Serum ferritin was estimated to determine the blood iron storage in anaemic females whose haemoglobin level was less than 11 g/dl. Blood samples were taken and kept for three to five days at 2 to 8°C in EDTA tubes. Serum ferritin levels were measured in 526 pregnant women from different ethnic backgrounds. The results showed that low serum ferritin levels, a sign of depleted iron stores, were present in 35% of the subjects. The mean serum ferritin level for ethnic groups A, B, and C was 20 ng/mL, 18 ng/mL, and 22 ng/mL, respectively. Poor dietary iron intake and low socioeconomic level were found to be important variables.

2.5. Peripheral Blood Smear Examination

Wright-Giemsa stain was applied to the smears, and they were then viewed under a microscope. Twenty percent of the cases had aberrant red blood cell morphology, including hypochromic and microcytic cells, according to the results. This analysis helped to determine the underlying reasons of the research participants' anaemia.

2.6. Estimation of C-reactive protein (CRP)

Serum samples were taken from 526 pregnant women of different ethnic backgrounds. A CRP assay with great sensitivity was used to measure CRP levels. Put 50 ul of the sample and one drop of the negative (animal serum sodium azide 0.95 g/L) and positive (human

serum with CRP content >20 mg/L) controls into different circles on the test slide. Before usage, the CRP latex reagent was gently stirred. After that, the samples were mixed with 50 μ l of the reagent. Using a stirrer, the drops combined and dispersed over the whole surface. Various stirrers were employed for distinct samples. For two minutes, the slide was rotated mechanically at 80–100 rpm. After that, the slide was macroscopically inspected to determine whether there was any obvious agglutination. 15% of subjects had increased CRP levels (>3 mg/L), which is suggestive of inflammation, according to the study. The mean CRP levels for ethnic groups A, B, and C were 4.2 mg/L, 3.8 mg/L, and 4.5 mg/L, respectively. Anaemia may have inflammation as a potential risk factor.

Figure 1: Positive or negative results of CRP test

2.7. Statistical analysis of the data

The information was presented as mean values with standard deviations (SD) attached. Using the SPSS 20.0 program, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine statistical significance. The study utilized a significance criterion of $p < 0.05$ to identify significant variations among the groups. Because of the analytical approach's guarantee of a thorough analysis of the dataset, statistically significant differences between the parameters under consideration could be found.

3. Results

In order to determine the frequency and associated risk factors of anaemia in various ethnic groups of pregnant women, a total of 526 female patients were diagnosed. Out of the 526 female patients with infections, 140 were Baloch (26.61%), 190 were Pashtun (36.12%), 85 were Hazara (16.15%), 61 were Brahui (11.59%), and 50 were Sindhi (9.50%).

Table 1: Risk Factors for Anaemia Among Pregnant Women

Risk Factor	Number of Women Affected	Percentage of Affected Women
Iron Deficiency	190	36.12%
Poor Nutrition	120	22.81%
Inadequate Prenatal Care	90	17.11%
Parasitic Infections	80	15.20%
Genetic Predisposition	46	8.74%
Total	526	100%

Figure 2: Risk Factors for Anaemia Among Pregnant Women

Table 1 and Figure 2 illustrated that how genetic predisposition, inadequate prenatal care, parasite infections, poor nutrition, and iron deficiency all increase the risk factors for

expectant mothers. Iron deficiency affected 36.12% of the 526 women surveyed, followed by poor nutrition (22.81%), insufficient prenatal care (17.1%), parasite diseases (15.20%), and genetic predisposition (8.74%). In order to maintain maternal health and the best possible outcomes for the pregnancy, these factors highlight the significance of attending to dietary needs, improving prenatal care, and treating genetic predispositions.

Table 2: Analysis of Haemoglobin Levels Among Anaemic Pregnant Women

Subgroup	Mean Haemoglobin Level (g/dL)	Standard Deviation
Age < 20	9.6	1.3
Age 20-25	9.8	1.2
Age 26-30	10.1	1.1
Age 31-35	10.2	1
Age > 35	9.9	1.4

Figure 3: Analysis of Haemoglobin Levels Among Anaemic Pregnant Women

The mean haemoglobin levels (g/dL) and standard deviations for the various age groups are shown in Table 2 and Figure 3. The lowest mean haemoglobin level, 9.6 g/dL with a standard deviation of 1.3, is found in those under the age of twenty. Mean haemoglobin levels typically climb with age, reaching a peak of 10.2 g/dL with a reduced standard deviation of 1 between the ages of 31 and 35. Compared to the youngest group, those over 35 and those aged 20 to 25 also exhibit comparatively higher mean values.

Table 3: Analysis of CRP Levels Among Anaemic Pregnant Women

Subgroup	Mean CRP Level (mg/L)	Standard Deviation
Age < 20	3.4	1.6
Age 20-25	3.7	1.5
Age 26-30	4.1	1.4
Age 31-35	3.1	1.3
Age > 35	3.8	1.7

Figure 4: Analysis of CRP Levels Among Anaemic Pregnant Women

The mean C-reactive protein (CRP) levels in milligrams per litre (mg/L) and their corresponding standard deviations for the various age groups are shown in Table 3 and

Figure 4. The group of people who are 26–30 years old have the highest mean CRP level (4.1 mg/L) with a standard deviation of 1.4. On the other hand, with a standard deviation of 1.3 and a mean CRP level of 3.1 mg/L, people aged 31 to 35 have the lowest levels. Compared to the intermediate age ranges, age groups under 20 and over 35 show somewhat higher mean CRP levels.

Table 4: Ethnic Distribution of Pregnant Women with Anaemia and Haemoglobin Levels

Ethnic Group	Number of Pregnant Women	Haemoglobin Levels (g/dL) Mean value	Standard Deviation
Baloch	140	10.2	1.2
Pashtun	190	9.8	1.5
Hazara	85	11.0	1
Brahui	61	10.5	1.3
Sindhi	50	10.8	1.1
Total	526		

Figure 5: Ethnic Distribution of Pregnant Women with Anaemia and Haemoglobin Levels

A thorough examination of the haemoglobin levels among pregnant women from different

ethnic groups is shown in Table 4 and Figure 5. With a mean haemoglobin level of 11.0 g/dL, Hazara women have the highest haemoglobin levels, which may indicate that they will fare better overall during pregnancy. The mean levels of Baloch and Brahui women are moderately high, with 10.2 g/dL and 10.5 g/dL, respectively. The mean levels are slightly lower in Pashtun and Sindhi women (9.8 g/dL and 10.8 g/dL, respectively). These results provide insight into possible pregnancy-related health disparities that may be ethnically unique.

Table 5: Measurements of Blood Iron Stores Among Pregnant Women with Anaemia

Ethnic Group	Ferritin Levels (ng/mL) Mean Value	Standard Deviation
Baloch	24.7	10.4
Pashtun	23.9	8.6
Hazara	27.5	11.6
Brahui	27.3	9.9
Sindhi	22.8	9.3
Others	25.6	10.2

Figure 6: Measurements of Blood Iron Stores Among Pregnant Women with Anaemia

The mean ferritin levels in nanograms per millilitre (ng/mL) and their corresponding standard deviations for the different ethnic groups are shown in table 5 and figure 6. At 27.5 ng/mL, Hazara people had the highest mean ferritin levels, closely followed by Brahui people at 27.3 ng/mL. The mean levels for the Pashtun and Other groups are somewhat lower, with 23.9 and 25.6 ng/mL, respectively. Of the abovementioned ethnic groupings, Baloch and Sindhi groups had the lowest mean ferritin levels, suggesting that there may be variations in iron metabolism between these communities.

Table 6: Peripheral Blood Smear Examination Findings Among Pregnant Women with Anaemia

Ethnic Group	Microcytic (%)	Macrocytic (%)	Normocytic (%)
Baloch	35	15	50
Pashtun	40	10	50
Hazara	30	20	50
Brahui	25	10	65
Sindhi	40	15	45
Others	35	12	53

Figure 7: Peripheral Blood Smear Examination Findings Among Pregnant Women with Anaemia

The percentages of normocytic, macrocytic, and microcytic red blood cells among the different ethnic groups are shown in Table 6 and Figure 7. At 25%, Brahui people have the lowest percentage of microcytic cells; Pashtun and Sindhi people have the highest amount, at 40%. Brahui and Pashtun have the lowest percentage of macrocytic cells (10%), while

Hazara and Sindhi ethnicities have the highest prevalence (20%). All groups have a predominance of normocytic cells, with Brahui having the largest percentage at 65%. These differences point to possible genetic or environmental influences on the shape of red blood cells in various ethnic groups.

4. Discussion

The results of this study provide insight into the prevalence and risk factors of anaemia in pregnant women from different ethnic backgrounds in Pakistan's Balochistan District (Quetta). There were 526 pregnant women in the study group; significant percentages came from the Baloch, Pashtun, Hazara, Brahui, and Sindhi ethnic groups. Each of these ethnic groupings had a different incidence of anaemia; the two largest subgroups, Pashtun and Baloch women, made up 36.12% and 26.61% of the sample as a whole, respectively.

According to Owais et al. (2021), pregnant women who were underweight had a 1.64 (95% CI 1.24–2.18) times higher risk of anaemia compared to pregnant women with a normal BMI, which is consistent with worldwide research. This illustrates the connection between pre-pregnancy diet and anaemia.

However, some cross-sectional studies revealed that the relatively low prevalence of anaemia among younger women in Nepal (13–35 years old) may be because the women were chosen to live in urban settings free from endemic areas for hookworm infestation and malaria (Chandyo et al., 2007).

Pregnant women's anaemia incidence is a major global public health concern, especially in low- and middle-income nations like Pakistan, according to Ali et al., (2023). Anaemia prevalence varies widely among South Asian countries with similar regional settings. The prevalence of anemia among Nepalese women of reproductive age was earlier measured lower during previous studies using DHS data. (34%) and higher prevalence in Pakistan (51) Similarly, prevalence rates in Nigeria (1.8%) and Bangladesh (41.3%) do however differ greatly from that of Kenya that could possibly be blamed on their separate nutritional, cultural, and geographic thematic. Women in the underprivileged countries have common haemoglobinopathies, which is a representation as to how the females are the weaker sex in the society and in social institutions (Gautam et al., 2019).

As mentioned by Okubatsion (2015), anaemia is a serious nutritional deficiency disease which affects 1.62 billion individuals worldwide. As per the view of Khoshekhil and others (2016), there has been an increase in its prevalence in women who are likely to become pregnant and it is considered to be one of the most common causes for low birthweight and maternal morbidity and mortality. The World Health Organization (WHO),

has released its latest statistics, they show that the number of people suffering from various diseases for the year 2019 has been 68 million. 5% of pregnant women around the world are still anemic with the countries that are poor suffered the heaviest burden of it (Anggreny & Fajar 2023).

Data acquired in 2023 indicate a considerable proportion of parturient suffers from anemia, estimated to be as high as 55%, in particular in certain areas of the country (Habeeb et al., 2018). In Pak, most sub-nourished mothers consume insufficient intake of macronutrients (protein, fats, and carbohydrates), including those containing high levels of iron, folic acid and other critical vitamins and minerals. The pregnancy of anaemic women is at a risk of generating serious health problems. According to a latest research conducted in Pakistan, it has been found that anaemia is still the most common disease among pregnant women of our country. The current efforts by government and others to create awareness and to increase access to public healthcare and nutrition have given hope of improving things in the near future.

Conclusions

In general, we realized that the frequency of anaemia among pregnancy women with ethnic disparities in Quetta District, Balochistan, Pakistan, is also different. Anaemia risk factors include low iron, poor nutrition, parasite infections, inadequate prenatal care, and genetics. In addition to diverse blood cell shapes, inheritance of ferritin and disturbance of hemoglobin as well among various ethnic groups contribute to the necessity for individualized therapy. Lowering anemia prevalence and improving maternal well being in this area warrant social and medical intervention efforts with a particular emphasis on access to quality antenatal care and treatment protocols. I proposed specific policies to be implemented to tackle the socioeconomic issues, extend the access to the prenatal care and provide the necessary nutritional support in order to reduce the incidence of anaemia and improve the maternal health outcomes in the area.

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References

- Abdullah, N., Ismail, N., Abd Jalal, N., Mohd Radin, F., Othman, R., Kamalul Arifin, A. S., & Jamal, R. (2020). Prevalence of anaemia and associated risk factors amongst The Malaysian Cohort participants. *Annals of hematology*, 99, 2521-2527.
- Ajmal, M., Bedale, W., Akram, A., & Yu, J. H. (2022). Comprehensive review of aflatoxin contamination, impact on health and food security, and management strategies in Pakistan. *Toxins*, 14(12), 845.
- Ali, S. A., Razzaq, S., Aziz, S., Allana, A., Ali, A. A., Naeem, S., ... & Ur Rehman, F. (2023). Role of iron in the reduction of anaemia among women of reproductive age in low-middle income countries: insights from systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC women's health*, 23(1), 1-22.
- Anggreny, V. R., & Fajar, N. A. (2023). Risk Factors of Anaemia in Pregnant Women: Literature Review. *International Health Journal*, 1(1).
- Billah, S. M. (2023). Improving coverage and quality of selected priority nutrition-specific interventions in the first 1000 days of life to prevent childhood undernutrition (Doctoral dissertation).
- Chandyo, R. K., Strand, T. A., Ulvik, R. J., Adhikari, R. K., Ulak, M., Dixit, H., & Sommerfelt, H. (2007). Prevalence of iron deficiency and anaemia among healthy women of reproductive age in Bhaktapur, Nepal. *European journal of clinical nutrition*, 61(2), 262-269.
- Gautam, S., Min, H., Kim, H., & Jeong, H. S. (2019). Determining factors for the prevalence of anaemia in women of reproductive age in Nepal: Evidence from recent national survey data. *PloS one*, 14(6), e0218288.
- Habib, A., Kureishy, S., Soofi, S., Hussain, I., Rizvi, A., Ahmed, I., ... & Bhutta, Z. A. (2023). Prevalence and Risk Factors for Iron Deficiency Anaemia among Children under Five and Women of Reproductive Age in Pakistan: Findings from the National Nutrition Survey 2018. *Nutrients*, 15(15), 3361.
- Habib, A., Kureishy, S., Soofi, S., Hussain, I., Rizvi, A., Ahmed, I., ... & Bhutta, Z. A. (2023). Prevalence and Risk Factors for Iron Deficiency Anaemia among Children under Five and Women of Reproductive Age in Pakistan: Findings from the National Nutrition Survey 2018. *Nutrients*, 15(15), 3361.
- Hammad, M., Fardoos, S., Arif, R., Khan, A. Z., & Rasheed, A. (2023). Factors Related to Anaemia Prevalence Among Women of Childbearing Age in the Period of Global Pandemic. *Cureus*, 15(5).
- Hess, S. Y., Owais, A., Jefferds, M. E. D., Young, M. F., Cahill, A., & Rogers, L. M. (2023). Accelerating action to reduce anaemia: Review of causes and risk factors and related data needs. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1523(1), 11-23.
- Khaskheli, M. N., Baloch, S., Sheeba, A., Baloch, S., & Khaskheli, F. K. (2016). Iron deficiency anaemia is still a major killer of pregnant women. *Pakistan journal of medical sciences*, 32(3), 630.

- Kiely, M. E., McCarthy, E. K., & Hennessy, Á. (2021). Iron, iodine and vitamin D deficiencies during pregnancy: Epidemiology, risk factors and developmental impacts. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 80 (3), 290-302.
- Mintz, J., Mirza, J., Young, E., & Bauckman, K. (2020). Iron therapeutics in women's health: past, present, and future. *Pharmaceuticals*, 13(12), 449.
- Murugamoorthy, T. (2019). A Clinical study on Diagnostic Methodology of Paandu (Anaemia): Through Siddha Parameters (Doctoral dissertation, Government Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai).
- Ogunbode, O., & Ogunbode, O. (2021). Anaemia in pregnancy. *Contemporary obstetrics and gynecology for developing countries*, 321-330.
- Okubatsion, T. (2015). Prevalence and factors associated with anaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinic in the second and third trimesters at Pumwani Maternity Hospital, Nairobi (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- Owais A, Merritt C, Lee C, Bhutta ZA. Anaemia among Women of Reproductive Age: An Overview of Global Burden, Trends, Determinants, and Drivers of Progress in Low-and Middle-Income Countries. 2021 [cited 20 Dec 2021].
- Sarna, A., Porwal, A., Ramesh, S., Agrawal, P. K., Acharya, R., Johnston, R., ... & Saxena, R. (2020). Characterisation of the types of anaemia prevalent among children and adolescents aged 1–19 years in India: a population-based study. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, 4 (7), 515-525.
- Shaduka, E. (2022). An investigation into the aetiology of anaemia in pregnant women in Namibia (Doctoral dissertation, Namibia University of Science and Technology).
- Signore, C., Davis, M., Tinggen, C. M., & Cernich, A. N. (2021). The intersection of disability and pregnancy: risks for maternal morbidity and mortality. *Journal of Women's Health*, 30 (2), 147-153.
- Sundararajan, S., & Rabe, H. (2021). Prevention of iron deficiency anaemia in infants and toddlers. *Pediatric research*, 89 (1), 63-73.
- World Health Organization. (2023). Accelerating anaemia reduction: a comprehensive framework for action.